

Highly green luminescent of indium doped CdTe colloidal quantum dots

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Abstract

Quantum dots gains enhancing interest in scientific and industrial area for optoelectronics applications (1) due to its unique optical and electrical properties such as bandgap tunability, high absorption coefficient, multiexciton generation, delivery of hot electrons (2) and also low cost and solution processability (3). This research work describes the colloidal synthesized of 3-Mercaptopropionic acid (3-MPA) capped CdTe QD and Indium doped (1%, 3%, 5%) CdTe quantum dots were accomplished. All these procedures were carried out in aqueous medium at air atmosphere. Highly green luminescent of CdTe and Indium doped CdTe colloidal quantum dots of size dependent band gaps were determined from UV-Vis spectra. The photoluminescence properties of the prepared quantum dots were characterized by using photoluminescence spectroscopy. The structural and morphologies were studied by HRTEM and X-Ray diffractometer. The formation of Indium doped quantum dots and the capping effect of the thiol group was investigated by using FTIR studies. Using DLS the particle Size ware analyzed.

Keyword: Quantum dots, Optoelectronics, CdTe, Doping

Reference

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